

Logical structure of clinical practice.

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16 May 2023

Clinical practice is complex enough to benefit from the use of computer information managements systems. This benefit comes in the form of organising and documenting clinical practice. In order to design an information management system of clinical practice, it is necessary to design first the logical structure of the clinical practice. This made-up logical structure is imposed on the clinical practice itself.

Finite-state machines provide a model that can help conceptualise clinical practice.

Seen as a finite-state machine, a patient goes through a series of states as a result of clinical interventions by health-care agents. The state-transition table shows which states you can move to, being in a given state, and reveals the patient-care protocol.

At a given time, a patient can only be in one clinical state. This clinical state can have multiple parameters (clinical variables) and, therefore, can be represented as a vector in a vector space where each clinical variable is represented as a coordinate or dimension in the vector space. A clinical state is then a cluster of vectors close together according to some metric.

A clinical intervention depends on the state a patient is in, but for a given state different clinical interventions are possible. (Clinical decision making must be documented.)

A clinical intervention (performed by a health-care agent) makes a patient transition from one state to another. A clinical intervention can be a medical, surgical or diagnostic.

A clinical event (not performed by a health-care agent) can also make a patient transition from one state to another. The nature of a clinical event can be unknown, like an infection event.

A particular clinical intervention always stands at a particular point in the process of patient care: it is linked to a certain clinical state.

Different aspects of patient care can be represented by different finite-state machines.

A complex clinical intervention, like a surgical procedure, can be represented as a separate finite-state machine by itself.

Data concepts:

- finite-state machine
- clinical state
- clinical intervention (procedure), performed by health-care agent
- clinical event (not initiated by health-care agent)
- health-care agent

Documentation of patient care:

- definition of finite-state machine by aspect of patient care and complex clinical intervention
- state-transition table (logic of state-to-state transitions)
- state-transition-log table (documentation of clinical interventions and clinical events)

Clinical decision making

Clinical decisions are based on the clinical state a patient is in. When, given a clinical state, different interventions are possible, there must be a method to evaluate the cost-benefit of each intervention.

The expected utility of an intervention according to the rational decision model is calculated as:

$$EU(a) = \sum_i P_i \cdot U(O_i)$$

where:

- P_i = probability of outcome i
- O_i = outcome
- $U(O_i)$ = utility assigned to that outcome

The utility function U encodes the agent's values.

Rather than guiding the decision process, this mathematical formula documents the reasoning behind a decision. The agent's values are not determined a priori, and then the expected utility for different actions (a) is calculated, and the one with highest expected utility is selected as the best action to take. Instead, the agent's values are *revealed* by the decisions the agent makes. The expected utility function is, therefore, a tool to document the values of the agent and the probabilities assigned to each outcome.

The only way to improve the decision-making process is by keeping a record of what was involved in making each decision. Such a record will be likely to reveal inconsistencies and contradictory value sets, as the research of Daniel Kahneman and Amos Tversky showed.

The source of these inconsistencies and contradictions, however, is that the utility function that encodes the agent's values is incorrect. The agent's value set must be modified in such a way that the rational-decision-model principle 'to choose action a that maximises expected utility' holds.

Claims of irrationality are dependent on inconsistency in the utility function. By making corrections to the claims made on values held, based instead on the actual decisions made, the thesis of irrationality is refuted. My values are not revealed by my claims, they are revealed by my choices.

Conclusion: There is no straightforward way to automate the process of selecting the best action to take, but there is a way to retrospectively account for the reasons behind the decisions made.

Diagnostic procedures

Diagnostic decision trees are numerous in scope and specificity. There's a need to build a taxonomy of diagnostic decision trees. Deciding which diagnostic procedure to use in the care of a patient is the first decision to make.

The first problem is how to represent diagnostic decision trees. They can be represented in many ways. A simple directed graph is adequate, but within the complexity of medical care, when decisions depend on combination of states, multiple conditions jointly produce an outcome, and transitions involve many-to-many relations, hypergraphs are a more flexible—although more complex—tool.

Although the logical structure and complexity of medical decisions can efficiently be represented by hypergraphs, the actual implementation and execution of a given medical decision tree in the care of a particular patient is best recorded as a finite-state-machine.

Once the problem of representation has been solved, the problem of classification comes next. Such a classification must take into account domain, scope and purpose.

This is the information technology perspective of this problem:

- Representation of the logical structure of medical decision trees as hypergraphs.
- Implementation of a medical decision tree in the care of a patient by means of a finite-state-machine.
- Organisation of decision trees (clinical protocols) as options to use in the care of patients.

This holds good for all medical decision trees, both diagnostic and therapeutic.

Medical treatment scheme

Efficiency in medical practice requires the establishment of predetermined protocols of clinical decisions and patient-care management. These protocols can be represented as finite-state-

machines. There is a general clinical workflow, and the course of action taken for a particular patient at a particular time. The key is to establish a relation between a patient's clinical progress and the general clinical-care workflow: Where in this workflow does a particular patient stand at this point in time?

When multiple workflows or protocols are available for a given condition, the choice of which one to follow must be documented. Deviations from protocols must also be documented.

Medication

Medication is given according to a medical treatment scheme. Every medication-administration event must be recorded with a link to the medical treatment scheme, a time-stamp, and account of deviations from protocol. In addition, a follow-up note of response to therapy must be added.

Surgical procedures

The complexity of surgical procedures requires a finite-state-machine model.

The problem in surgery is record keeping in the face of a crisis, the moment when record keeping is actually most important. A surgical clerk may be necessary.

Anaesthesia

In parallel with a surgical procedure, the anaesthesia procedure also requires its own finite-state-machine model. Both the surgical and anaesthesia procedures, their events and clinical interventions, must be synchronised by timestamp matching.

Documentation in patient care

The problem of patient care documentation is that 'urgent matters crowd out important ones'. Electronic medical records typically have suboptimal user interfaces and unrealistic information models that make clinical record keeping an overwhelming task. The use of finite-state-machine models can significantly reduce this burden. In some overloaded situations, a clinical-care clerk may be the only solution.

The practice of medicine

The practice of medicine has two components: First, the design of medical protocols. Second, the application of these protocols to the care of particular patients.

Over time, these two functions have been isolated from each other. The first function has been gradually placed in the hands of insurance companies, professional institutions and hospital administrators. Physicians have been relegated to clinical technicians that do what they are expected to do. They have lost their autonomy. This is structurally a self-defeating approach based on health care as a for-profit business and loss of trust in physicians and nurses as health-care providers. It is a ‘disaster waiting to happen’ that has actually already happened.

The problem is that when you lose your autonomy and are treated as somebody who cannot be trusted, you end up becoming somebody that cannot be trusted. The loss of autonomy brings loss of judgement.

Nurses and physicians cannot give up their ability to make clinical decisions. If they do, they lose their humanity. In fact, there is talk about their substitution by artificial-intelligence agents. The loss of autonomy by health-care providers has all the seeds of failure. We see a perfect storm in the making.

Shifting our trust from moral agents with medical expertise to machines designed by profit-seeking executives is the sure path to failure, as we already see.

The complexity of medical knowledge does require the use of computer technology, but the design of computer systems in medicine must be in the hands of health-care practitioners. Successful computer systems must be designed by those who are going to use them.